

Opinions on planning, managing, and controlling programs, projects, or long-term contracts

Abstract:

This work reviews several methods outlined and applied in the course of concrete work carried out by the author in the past. The methods described are summarized here for discussion and dissemination. This paper is divided into three parts. The first part immediately highlights the financial significance of the area under the expenditure-over-time curve for comparative estimation of the financial cost of alternative projects or for comparing different possible reconfigurations in cases of program revision. Then, after recalling the importance of appropriately using scale effects in budgeting - starting from the trend of "historical" data series of expected and actual disbursements for a long-term project or program, which gradually emerge during implementation in the field - this work proposes obtaining two functions (e.g., linearized with best fit), whose intersection allows us to provide the best estimate when analysing the time and cost of completing the program or project under consideration. The second part proposes integrating, mathematically and/or graphically, time and costs into a single progress parameter, since both time and costs are always two external constraints contractually established for the execution of a project or program. Thus, the third part, among other reminders, encourages the "rediscovery" during the planning or program review phase of the two polar approaches "as soon as possible" and "as late as possible" in allocating activities over the time allowed by the program. The goal is to optimize both economic and financial aspects, without, however, excessively criticizing the entire project duration. Failure to do so typically exposes the implementing organization to contractual penalties and/or sanctions. The same section discusses the proper use of work acceleration in both the planning and program review phases. The conclusions summarize how the highlighted elements and their interconnected elements are among those to be considered when assessing the systemic risk of a project, program, or long-term contract.

Keywords: Management, Development, Planning, Programming, Control, Projects, Programs, Contracts, Risks

Clarification preface: This work is a practitioner paper and does not aim to reinvent the mathematics of project control, but rather to draw attention to some phenomena that have often been encountered in real projects. Therefore, it is based on professional experience and offers practical insights to be discussed and further verified for practical application. The actual purpose of this paper is to discuss the offered set of practical observations derived from long-term project experience. Although the topics addressed may appear heterogeneous, they are linked by a common objective: improving planning and control decisions in order to reduce the systemic risk inherent in large and long-duration projects and contracts.

1. Introduction

This work reviews some methods outlined and applied in the course of concrete work carried out by the author in the past. These methods were partially presented in various formats by

the author at the "AICE Days 2017 and 2018" meetings and are available in the Proceedings of the said Days of the Italian Association for Economic Engineering (AICE), which operates in collaboration with The International Cost Engineering Council (ICEC). The methods described are summarized here for discussion and dissemination.

Anyone with business knowledge, or knowledge of planning techniques, or who has prepared and managed a significant project or contract, knows well that on a cost-time graph (see Fig. 1), the area under the expenditure curve representing it (known in jargon as an "S" curve, although the trend may vary) serves as a generic "qualitative" indicator of the financial cost of a program, project, or contract, as the case may be. A program, excluding cases where it means time schedule, is considered a set of multiple projects that are integrated with each other, not only logically, but also form a single whole for achieving a specific objective. Individually or in an integrated manner, projects, or programs, are the subject of various forms of binding contract between the parties involved.

Figure 1

The aforementioned financial burden is particularly significant in long-term programs, projects, or contracts. In these cases, the generic "qualitative" index suggested above can be a heuristic tool to provide useful insights into other important considerations, some of which are proposed below, since both time and costs are always two external constraints contractually imposed on the execution of a project, program, or contract. To further clarify the discussion, we can introductorily examine the various diagrams shown in Fig. 2 below:

Figure 2

They all refer to different payment options for a job with duration (t) and total outlay (P). Case (a) presents a payment totally advanced at the beginning of the work; case (d) represents a payment totally deferred to the end of the work; cases (b) and (c), however, are intermediate situations between the two extreme cases mentioned (i.e., on opposite poles).

It can be seen that the areas under the diagrams increase from zero in (d) to a maximum in (a), so it seems reasonable to say that small overall areas indicate convenience for the client

(because it shifts its disbursements forward in time), while conversely, large areas indicate convenience for the supplier or contractor (because they spread the expected payments better, from their perspective). In other words, the area under the disbursement diagram can be an indicator, for the client, of the financial burden of the project, while for the contractor or supplier it can represent an indicator of the financing of the project that they should provisionally assume in view of the final profit.

Equitable situations, even if this term is always subject to "ideological asymmetries", are reached when the actual trends in disbursements by the client closely mirror the actual trends in disbursements by the supplier or contractor made during the course of the work.

In any case, the area of a disbursement diagram alone is completely inadequate as an element for quantitative evaluations. Indeed, by way of example, from the following Figures 3.1 and 3.2 it can be seen that, even with the same underlying area, situations (a) and (b) give rise to significantly different financial findings, since identical areas at different distances from the y-axis have different financial content.

Figure 3

This does not mean, however, that the financial significance attributable to the area covered by the disbursement diagram can contain only a "heuristic" value, but it also contains a practical application value, as can be seen during the course of the work and in the illustration shown below.

2. Discussion

2.1 First Part

Experience shows that large, multi-year programs and projects, typical of institutional settings (especially public ones), are rarely launched with a basic project already defined and analytically computable. Instead, there typically exists a "meta-project" poorly defined except in terms of concepts or objectives, or at least in very general terms. Such "meta-project" serves as the basis for a sort of initial estimation plan, usually based on overall analogy or for individual large parts. The meta-project can also be used during the tender phase (where it is better defined by the bidders based on the tender conditions), and the negotiation phase allows for competitive play, combined with the client's foresight and expertise, to produce its cost-containment effects. Typically, for example, cases of similar projects are sought, even on a larger and smaller scale, and cost and time estimates are analytically taken into account for

"scale effects." Regarding these effects, which impact the results of the initial estimates, it seems appropriate to open a brief parenthesis to highlight the following.

In construction practice, it is noted that the costs of systems, works, or their components do not always increase linearly, that is, in proportion to their size, capacity, or overall dimensions. Often, as occurs in large industrial plants (chemical, petrochemical, and power generation), specific costs (c_s), also called unit costs — given by the ratio between total cost and capacity — decrease as the size increases, even as the total cost (C_T) increases (as occurs in Fig. 4 below, for example, in power plants, where costs per unit of installed power are usually expressed in \$/MW or \$/kW and the total cost is in \$).

Figure 4 - Economies of scale effects

Technical-economic literature (see for example J.E.Ullmann - Quantitative methods of business management – SCHAUM series – Italian edition 1985 – pages 3-4) underlines how it has been demonstrated that on the basis of the costs of many economic functions (and those of machines and plants as a function of the capacity of the plants) a very general empirical relationship of the type results:

$$C = a \cdot K^b \quad (1)$$

where C is the cost, K the capacity, (a) and (b) are constant.

When $0 < b < 1$, that is, b is between zero and one, the cost C has a lower rate of increase than that of the capacity K ; their trend is that shown in Figure N.4 above, and we can affirm that "economies of scale" exists. However, when (b) is greater than 1, then we would speak of "diseconomies of scale".

The consequence of all this is that if the relation (1), $C = a \cdot K^b$, were applied to two distinct but similar cases of plants, works or their components, we would have (identifying the two different cases with subscripts 1 and 2) that:

$$C_1 = a \cdot K_1^b \quad (2)$$

$$C_2 = a \cdot K_2^b \quad (3)$$

Dividing member by member and simplifying (*a*) we obtain:

$$\frac{C_1}{C_2} = \left(\frac{K_1}{K_2}\right)^b \quad (4)$$

a relationship that allows the costs of a new plant to be estimated based on a scaling exponent (*b*) when the costs and capacity of another similar plant of a different size are known. For instance, the same SCHAUM Series reference cited above also provides some examples, in which a value of (*b*) equal to 0.7 is assumed for power plants; this value is considered characteristic of this type of plant.

Furthermore, it is reported in the UNIDO manual - W. Behrens – P.M. Hawranek - “Manual for the preparation of Industrial Feasibility Studies” 2nd edition – 1995, that cost scale exponents are published (for example by the Institution of Chemical Engineers – London), but they must be regularly verified through prices practiced in tenders or competitive procedures and it is also necessary to update historical data due to inflation. A list of some typical exponents, published in the aforementioned UNIDO manual is the following:

Estimated scaling exponent for different plant components

PLANT COMPONENTS	Estimated scaling exponent
Tanks (spherical)	0.7
Electric motors	0.8
Columns, Towers	0.7 (constant diameter)
Heat exchangers	0.65 to 0.95
Piping	0.7 to 0.9
Instrumentation and control	0.0

Table 1

It is worth noting that for rough estimates of orders of magnitude, an overall plant scaling exponent can be used. However, caution is needed when applying the method described here to complete plants without using a market database: a best-fit (e.g., with Excel) with an exponential function for even a few pairs of cost and capacity data (C_i , K_i) allows for finding an appropriate exponent and limiting significant risks of overestimation or underestimation. For example, in the case of chemical plants with reactors used in batches, the exponent may be very different than for similar plants intended for continuous operation. Furthermore, exponential factors may differ considerably depending on the site and available infrastructure, as occurs when comparing cases for different projects in different countries, which are differently positioned in terms of local development, infrastructure, services, legislation, etc. In these cases, it is advisable to break down the plants, works, or their components into individual systems or homogeneous parts and proceed with a more accurate analysis. Obviously, project-based cost estimation founded on detailed bills of quantities (as per related basic design) remains the best option, even when scale effects are present. If not handled with care and expertise, these scaling techniques can lead to initial estimation errors, i.e., already in the development and planning phases, which are difficult to correct later in the design, tender, negotiation, and contract award phases. Such errors, however, are even more

difficult to correct in the execution and implementation phases (construction, commissioning, or project and program review).

However, no matter how accurate the estimation process and no matter how scrupulous the cost and schedule overrun risk analysis, ultimately, in practice, an estimate remains an estimate and can only serve as a general but approximate reference, always subject to necessary modifications. On the other hand, truly analogous or similar reference projects are always quite rare and difficult to find. Feedback on experience and data on them is often delayed and affected by economic issues (e.g., reference bases, exchange rates, and inflation), confidentiality (security and market issues), commercial issues (niche vs. competition), industrial, technological, environmental, and political-social factors, which increasingly demonstrate great variability and impact. Therefore, in reality—during execution, as a result of initial approximations—repeated planning occurs as the project progresses, accompanied by increases in costs and initially planned schedules. From these re-plannings, historical series of data can emerge that are useful for an analytical examination of trends.

In multi-year programs, the lifetime cost of a project (or the amount of other lifetime resources dedicated to it) is one of the most important parameters to identify during the planning phase (or during subsequent re-planning). However, for some very large, long-term projects — for example, infrastructure projects (for the construction of railway networks, highways, or networks in general, etc.), or for the decommissioning of large, abandoned industrial projects (e.g., nuclear power plants and facilities, or the remediation of vast, heavily damaged and polluted areas) — the lifetime cost not only varies (usually increasing) over the course of the project itself, but may also require the establishment of a structured team or even a full-fledged program management company. In these cases, systematic and periodic follow-up and planning reviews are carried out, including the timeline and the lifetime cost, which exhibit a trend over time. Precisely in these particular cases, trend analyses of the resources allocated to the project (e.g., historical series of expected disbursements in subsequent re-plannings during the project) and those actually employed can be a useful forecasting aid in monitoring and controlling the projects themselves.

Figure 5 - Trend Analysis during performance (e.g. construction) for the purpose of forecasting times and costs "to finish"

The point P_n of convergence of the trend line of lifetime resources with the trend line of resources actually employed throughout the various implementation phases takes on not only a reference value for the actual progress of the project, but also a predictive value for the possible end of the project itself and the amount of resources required (see Fig. 5). The trend

procedure conducted graphically or analytically therefore focuses project monitoring and control on the convergence point P_n . The geometric procedure of intersection of two trend lines on an (x,y) plane identifies the coordinates of the point P_n through the following system formed by the equations of the two trend lines found (e.g. with the least squares method or with the partial means procedure):

$$\begin{cases} y = a_1 + b_1(x) \\ y = a_2 + b_2(x) \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

It goes without saying that in those cases where the slopes of the two trend lines diverge (i.e., the average rate of increase in lifetime costs is greater than the rate of outlay for the project's implementation), it means that the project is out of control and there is a risk that its implementation will never be realized. If the two trend functions were not linear, but were two different generic functions $f(x)$ and $g(x)$, the reasoning would be completely identical except that the system would take the form:

$$\begin{cases} y = f(x) \\ y = g(x) \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Finally, in cases where long-term project management is entrusted to a fully-fledged management company, it should be kept in mind that implementation delays (e.g., $\Delta t = \text{Delta } t$ in the Figure 5), during which little or no project progress is made, automatically translate into a rise in lifetime costs due to the overhead and operating costs that the company itself (or the responsible team) requires, as is clearly visible from the red box in Fig. 5, which represents a true "loss" (i.e., a general cost) for the project. Therefore, this is not just the usual increase in overhead costs, to which these costs are also subject over time. Finally, it is worth emphasizing that the trend proposed here is more accurate and reliable the more data is available, which occurs in the advanced implementation phase of the program or project.

2.2 Second Part

There is a "mandatory" aspect – also of a contractual nature – for management control in relation to the initially planned time, cost, and other resource values. The mandatory nature for management control also arises from the fact that for the Client, whether institutional, public, or private, during ordinary management, not only the total cost of the project (C_t) and the final time (t_f) within which it must be completed ought to remain unchanged (i.e., the immovable position of P_0 in Fig. 6), but also the shape of the disbursement curve, whether S-shaped or otherwise, ought remain unchanged. Naturally, if the deviations that are revealed during the course of the project are not recoverable, extraordinary management actions would necessarily arise and therefore re-planning and re-programming (from P_0 to P_0'), obviously followed by re-contracting (due to variations). It is perhaps worth pointing out that at each re-planning the point (P_0') can be approximately determined with the trend method illustrated in 2.1. First Part.

“Economic and Temporal Progress Indexes” are not adequate:

“Economic Progress” at generic time $t_x = (C_x/C_t)$ is not representative of real progress.

“Temporal Progress” at generic time $t_x = (t_x/t_f)$ is not representative of real progress.

Furthermore consider:

$$\int_{t_0}^{t_f} S(t) \neq \int_{t_0}^{t'_f} S'(t) \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta S = \frac{\int_{t_0}^{t'_f} S'(t) - \int_{t_0}^{t_f} S(t)}{\int_{t_0}^{t'_f} S(t)} \quad (8)$$

Figure 6 - Review of planning at time t_x due to overruns of times and/or costs

Recent ICMS (International Cost Management Standard) still appear to be not very widespread, and traditional Earned Value management concepts and procedures—often considered unwieldy — do not yet appear to have sufficiently permeated the public and private procurement sectors.

The use of an application proposal for a "Progress Indicator" in an institutional/contractual context appears highly appropriate, not only for the contractual implications to which a progress control and reporting is usually associated. Such a proposal arises from the fact that it is not uncommon, in some large public projects, to give management significance to the concepts of economic progress and temporal progress, defined as the ratio between actual values (of time and costs) and those of the full-life budget or program total. The mere flowing of time and the increase in expected disbursements, or their specific ratios to contractual values, are not in themselves — especially when taken individually — significant indicators of project progress. Therefore, the management control procedures for an institutional project, through analysis of deviations from the plan, must always have mandatory and priority value, but must be based on indicators that are as representative of reality as possible. It is worth noting that in the framework of the above said indicators (based on ratios of time and costs) if the increase in the actual costs (or times) accrued in a given period is equivalent to the increases (overruns) in total cost or total time to complete, the actual economic or time progress, in that period, is eroded and may become substantially zero. To put it another way, if the goal is to travel 1000 km in 10 days, or 100 km/day on average, but as the first 100 km are completed, the target shifts by the same amount, achieving it becomes a daunting undertaking. The same thing may happen with “managerial control” using progress indicators based on time or cost ratios.

Figure 7 – Lack of representativeness of economic or temporal progress as defined above, as much more as in vicinity of the conditions [$(t_a - t_i) = (t_s - t_f)$; $(\Delta C_a = \Delta C_t)$]

A graphical demonstration is possible in Fig. 7, where, having assumed the period $(t_a - t_i)$ to be unitary, the incremental ratio of the actual figures is the increase ΔC_a . If, during the implementation period, forecast conditions arise such that the whole-life cost increases by an increment ΔC_t exactly equal to the increase in the actual figures ΔC_a , it appears that, based on the linear trend, it is as if another period of equal (unitary) amount were added at the end, from t_f to t_s . This, in practice, erodes the value of the economic progress (rendering it practically zero in the case of a linear trend).

Therefore, it appears that, at any point during the project's execution, it is more significant and correct, in order to determine a more objective and realistic progress, to refer to another differently formulated work progress indicator.

Furthermore, when comparing different plans, without defining an appropriate, independent, and different progress indicator (based, for example, on man-hours or physically objective quantities), it may be misleading to assume only the aforementioned "progress" in costs or times, or their indicators and values, as elements of comparative judgment or as elements representative of the project program's performance. For example, it is difficult to express an exact, comparable, and truthful judgment on the progress (physical, temporal, or economic) achieved in each year of implementation, in the different periods (two-year, five-year, etc.), and over the entire lifespan, when there are continuous changes in re-planning; this can lead to "losing" awareness or even no longer considering the true initial reference. For this reason, an appropriate reflection is proposed to evaluate if:

- the area under the S-shaped expenditure curve for each plan is significant (along with other traditional indicators such as size, NPV, IRR, break-even point, payback periods, etc.) as a comparison indicator between different plans; and
- an index (Q) may be appropriate as an integrated cost-time progress indicator, to be evaluated on a case-by-case basis; and
- the index (Q) may be the ratio between the area under the S-shaped cost-time curve relating to actual costs up to a given point in time and the area under the S-shaped cost-time curve

relating to total costs and times, i.e., actual costs and forecasts to be completed from that point forward, as it results from the re-planning at that point in time.

Referring to the following Fig.N.8 we would have:

A = (Area under the cost-time "S" curve relating to the actual disbursement up to t_a) → blue

B = (Area under the cost-time "S" curve relating to the Estimate Disbursement up to t_f) → red

$$Q = \frac{A}{A + B} \quad (9)$$

Figure 8 – Disbursement curve integrated area at any point in time t_x is : (Actual up to t_a)+ (Estimate Re-planned at time t_a up to t_f)

Such a progress indicator, freeing itself more from the intrinsic randomness of the forecast values of total times and costs over the entire life of the project, seems to take on a more appropriate value, since any variation (even simultaneous) in times and costs is immediately reflected in the progress status, which therefore becomes more "stable and reliable" in providing management with information on the actual status of a project.

For practical applications, we distinguish between: Case A: the ideal case of functions with continuous behaviour; Case B: the concrete case of functions with step-like behaviour. These applications are illustrated graphically and summarized mathematically in the graphs and concise boxes shown below for both cases.

2.2.1 Case A (Ideal): functions with continuous behaviour

Fig. 9 – Case A

2.2.2 Case B (Real): functions with step behaviour

Fig. 10 – Case B

Usually, one does not get a mathematical function (perhaps through "best fitting" operations on historical series), but data in a table as in Table 2 below; for example, with costs and times, in the form of a historical series of "cumulative values", divided between "actual values" (here, for example, up to 2017 - in blue) and "budgeted values" (in red) of a project started in the year 2000 and expected to "finish" in 2034.

Sums	Years	N°	Mln€
	2000	0	0,00
	2001	1	0,00
	2002	2	5,79
	2003	3	11,58
	2004	4	17,37
	2005	5	23,16
	2006	6	28,95
	2007	7	34,74
	2008	8	40,53
	2009	9	46,31
	2010	10	59,63
	2011	11	77,82
	2012	12	99,45
	2013	13	120,39
	2014	14	158,11
	2015	15	201,07
	2016	16	234,44
1428,24	2017	17	268,90
	2018	18	308,92
	2019	19	364,49
	2020	20	436,01
	2021	21	535,72
	2022	22	596,17
	2023	23	644,40
	2024	24	678,80
	2025	25	692,71
	2026	26	706,63
	2027	27	720,54
	2028	28	734,45
	2029	29	737,08
	2030	30	739,71
	2031	31	742,34
	2032	32	744,97
	2033	33	747,60
	2034	34	750,23
	2035	35	750,23
10880,78	2036	36	750,23
12309,02	TOTAL		12309,02
11,60%	Integrated Progress Index		

Table 2

With such data, a calculation with constant time intervals can be performed using the summation method [formula (11) - Fig. 10- Case B] – illustrated previously.

Any spreadsheet is sufficient to perform the necessary calculations. And yet... Perhaps in an age where quantum computers are on the horizon, it may seem anachronistic, but in both the first and second parts, these calculations appear complicated only in appearance (given the symbols for integrals and sigma), because if all the available and necessary data are reported for graphical representation on a sheet of graph paper (a now obsolete tool), trends can be easily obtained with a ruler and a set of set squares, while calculating areas is reduced to a trivial counting of small squares (see Fig. 11).

Simply as an example, the graph here below, in Fig. 11, shows the disbursement curve on graph paper. The blue section refers to the work already completed, while the red section refers to what remains to be completed according to the rescheduling shown in Table 2.

It can be noted that the errors made in the approximations are quite small and acceptable, amounting around one percent.

Therefore, the proposal for a new work progress index that integrates time and costs does not even require complicated tools and can be obtained even via simple graphical means in real time on the construction sites themselves if the data pairs on time and costs are available there.

Figure 11- Old instruments (historical series and graph paper)

2.3 Third Part

In light of the above, we can recall the close connection between the chronological schedules characterizing each project and the related financial burdens, especially in multi-year programs. This connection, well known to those involved in programming, distinguishes two planning criteria:

- a) a maximum advance criterion, consisting of the "as soon as possible" allocation along project time of "slack" activities (known in jargon as floating activities), i.e., those not coinciding with the critical line and therefore capable of sliding without compromising the overall duration;
- b) a maximum delay criterion, consisting of the "at the latest possible" allocation along project time of "slack" activities (known in jargon as floating activities), i.e., those not coinciding with the critical line and therefore capable of sliding without compromising the overall duration;

A clarification of the topic is possible by examining Figure 12 below, where the critical line is highlighted by the sequence of critical activities and the slack activities are allocated differently, depending on the criterion adopted.

It should be remembered, however, that the indiscriminate adoption of the maximum delay criterion, while reducing financial burdens by allowing financial commitment to slack activities as late as possible, also makes the program hypercritical (reducing margins), with the possibility of delaying the entire planned implementation if even one of the theoretically floating activities but practically made critical is delayed. For this reason, it is argued that the "at the latest" approach to planning should be excluded for programs that place a high value

on the final objective—for example, maintenance or construction programs for power generation plants, whose completion is dependent on the plant's start-up, not only for commercial reasons. Therefore, in these cases, the "as soon as possible" planning approach is adopted, leaving its opposite limited almost exclusively to applications for financial reasons, typically long-term. If we now consider that each program activity is (theoretically) linked to one or more payments, which can be hypothesized to be allocated differently throughout the entire program and/or the activity itself, it becomes clear that each program, as well as each program line, is characterized by its own disbursement curve. The maximum deferral criterion brings payments for non-critical activities closer to the final part of the program, thus reducing the area under the disbursement line. The maximum advance criterion has the opposite effect.

Figure 12

However, changes to the area under the disbursement curve can be achieved not only through the opportunistic allocation of program activities with the possibility of "floating," but also through, for example, changes to the contractual conditions for disbursement of payments, or through so-called acceleration bonuses. To understand the logic of this latter tool, the following concepts are needed.

Figure 13 - Which activities to accelerate

In theory, each program activity is considered to be associated with the following three times and costs:

- usual time t_M associated with a cost C_M greater than the minimum;
- normal time t_0 associated with a minimum cost C_0 ;
- accelerated time t_m associated with a cost C_m greater than the minimum;

and assuming that at t_0 we are dealing with neighborhoods of the direct and indirect cost curves of those same activities, which can be approximated by straight lines, we obtain Figure 13, from which we can deduce that the relationship

$$\phi = (C_m - C_0) / (t_0 - t_m) \quad (12)$$

This allows us to identify, in a program with many activities, which of them are most cost-effective to accelerate.

The theory of the Critical Path Method (CPM) tells us, in fact, that "The optimal project acceleration criterion consists in choosing, to reduce the completion time, those activities that have the lowest increase in direct cost per unit of time" (see L. Yu Chuen.Tao – Practical Applications of PERT and CPM – Franco Angeli Editore), that is, precisely those with the lowest ϕ .

3. Conclusion

It is quite clear that financial aspects—and therefore the associated systemic risk—are all the more relevant the more:

- the economic and temporal dimensions are significant (typical of the long term);
- the high level of dependence on external financing rather than the use of equity capital (which today is even increasingly financed through this method!);
- the high level of foreign currency (which may introduces exchange rate risk or instability in other economies) or the presence of a "common currency", typical of non-homogeneous free trade areas;
- the conditions for financing repayment are stringent and those for granting it are more lax (as the subprime crisis has shown).

All of the above factors, among others, given the unpredictability of the future on the long run, may suggest a systemic risk that grows exponentially with increasing time and capacity dimensions. This should lead to ever greater attention, during the initial planning phase, to the "area under the disbursement curve" and to the development of realistic and effective management, monitoring, and control tools, necessary during the long implementation of a program or project of the type considered here.

Any costly program accelerations, which would obviously affect the critical path and its constituent activities, implying advance and progressive payments, should lead to an assessment, among other things, on financial aspects to ensure that the benefits resulting from the acceleration are not less than the costs of achieving it.

If it is true that high systemic risks (see, for example, those of civil nuclear projects, or other major infrastructure or highly innovative projects) are more appropriate and sustainable for state-owned rather than private economies, then the opinions expressed here should be

relevant to public policy even more than to private policy. This work, therefore, cannot be considered only as a proposal for second-order optimization in executive management.

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